

CAIRT-PerReC

Earth Explorer 11 Phase A Performance
and Requirements Consolidation Study
(PerReC) – CAIRT

ESA/ESTEC contract 4000136480/21/NL/LF
PSD: “CAIRT L2(+) Product Specification Document”
Technical Note

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Deliverable number DEL-05

Reference Number: DEL-05-CAIRT-PhAPerReC-v3.1

Status: Final
Version/revision: 3.1
Date 01.12.2025

<i>ESA Study Contract Report</i>		
<i>ESA Contract</i> 4000136480/21/N L/LF	<i>Title</i> PSD: "CAIRT L2(+) Product Specification Document"	<i>Contractor</i> Karlsruhe Institut of Technology
<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document guides the specifications of the CAIRT Level-2a (L2a) and Level-2b (L2b) products. For completeness, the specifications of the Level-1b (L1b) files are also included. For each product, a preliminary assessment of its content is provided, covering also uncertainty estimates and quality indicators, along with an approximate estimation of product size and the auxiliary data required by each processor. The proposed product specifications have been cross-checked against the corresponding product files from MIPAS and GLORIA, as well as the CEEPS Interface Control Document (ICD).</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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DOCUMENT INFO

Reviewer

Reviewer	Organisation Short Name	E-Mail
All PIs		

Document Control

Document version #	Date	Changes Made/Comments
Draft	23.05.2024	For PM1
Version 1.0	14.10.2024	Added more consolidated estimation of the size of the different files. A placeholder for NRT L2a data has been inserted
Version 2.0	03.07.2025	Added product tree. Checked content of L1b and L2a files wrt CEEPS ICD, MIPAS, GLORIA output files and provided further details. Removed estimation of the size of the products (it will be described in an additional TN or in an appendix in a subsequent version of the document)
Version 3.0	06.10.2025	Final. Added description of L1b files. Added estimation of the size of the L1b and L2 products and discussion on L2a diagnostics
Version 3.1	01.12.2025	Small final edits

European Space Agency Contract Report

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Executive Summary

This document presents a preliminary assessment of the content and structure of the CAIRT Level-1b (L1b), Level-2a (L2a), and Level-2b (L2b) product files, along with a hint to the auxiliary data required by each processor. To support cross-validation of the proposed content, example product files from heritage missions and from the CAIRT prototype instrument, GLORIA, are provided. Approximate estimates of product sizes are also provided to give an initial sense of data volumes, facilitate sanity checks, and support alignment of expectations between the scientific and technical teams. These estimates also enable a preliminary qualitative comparison with the data products of other missions.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document aims to provide an overview of how CAIRT geophysical data requirements can be translated into actual Earth Observation (EO) data products. To this purpose a preliminary assessment of their content is provided, together with the information that needs to be exchanged between processors, and potential product sizes.

2. CAIRT product overview

Figure 1 provides an overview of the L2 processing scheme and data production tree of CAIRT, from L1b to L2b products, as well as the auxiliary data.

Figure 1 CAIRT L2 processing scheme and data production tree, depicted with an indicative time dimension (product latency increasing from top to bottom). Products are reported in green, auxiliary data inputs in purple, processors and lighter processing steps in dark and light blue, respectively.

The level 1b products are the output of L1 processor and contain geo-localized, radiometrically and spectrally calibrated spectra together with NESR information and data quality information.

L1b products are obtained from the FFT of the measured interferogram L0, using spectral, radiometric (and LOS) calibration files.

They are the input of L2a data processing, hence the content of L1b is determined by what is needed for L2a processing.

L2a products are the outputs of the L2a processor and contain the geophysical products obtained from the inversion of calibrated spectra contained in the L1b files.

L2b products are products derived from L2a data, directly linked to some mission objectives.

3. *Auxiliary data*

The list of the required auxiliary data for L1b, L2a and L2b processors is provided, but for detailed explanations please refer to the ATBD of the different algorithms.

4. *Product detailed format*

4.1 *Towards the selection of the proper format*

This section is meant to provide information on the file format and metadata to be used for CAIRT products, including information on filenames, global and variable attributes and unique product identifiers. However, the final decision on the format of CAIRT products has not been taken yet.

Here we report some considerations to be taken into account when selecting the format of the output files.

The choice of the format of the products has to be driven by the following needs:

- to select a file format that the users are already familiar with
- to use a base format that is already well supported in data-analysis packages
- to use a self-describing file format
- to build on experience from previous missions
- to adequate the format to the one that will be used by present and future missions, like the Sentinels.

The choice of both the content and the number of the provided output file has also to be driven by the need to limit the complexity for accessing and using the files by the users, distinguishing between information that is needed by the users and information that is needed for making diagnostics of the products and for special analyses.

The idea is to adopt established, self-describing, easy readable format.

The most common formats fulfilling these requirements and used for Earth Observation products are:

- HDF5 (used for example by JAXA for GOSAT)
- HDF5-EOS (used by NASA for many missions, like MLS)
- NetCDF-4 (used e.g. for MIPAS and for many new ESA missions, it will be used for EPS-SG, e.g. for IASI-NG)

Preference now is to adopt the netCDF-4 format with the netCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention [2]. This has been chosen also for the outputs of the CEEPS.

NetCDF-4:

- Is built on HDF5 format with an interface that is an extension of the NetCDF library.
- Is implemented like an intermediate layer between NetCDF and HDF5 API
- can group data (less effectively than HDF5) and compress them

- Every software which can open an HDF5 can also open a NetCDF-4
- is less complex than HDF5
- Sometime the file access is slower than HDF5
- Beginning with netCDF version 4.5.0, optional support is provided for accessing data from servers supporting the DAP4 protocol (this is very useful given the huge dimensions of these files).

This format is used for the outputs of Sentinel missions, as well as of many other missions both at ESA and NASA. Using netCDF-4 allows data users to choose from a wide range of data-analysis packages (like IDL, Matlab, Mathematica) and programming languages (Python, C, C++, Java and Fortran) to access the data. Furthermore, netCDF-4 format allows a lot of advanced features (grouping, compression, user defined data types, ...).

Conventions and units: Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions [5] is recommended where applicable. For the units, SI should be used where possible.

The CF metadata conventions are designed to promote the processing and sharing of files created with the [NetCDF API](#). The conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of the data. This enables users of data from different sources to decide which quantities are comparable, and facilitates building applications with powerful extraction, regridding, and display capabilities. The CF convention includes a standard name table, which defines strings that identify physical quantities.

4.2 File name conventions

A convention has to be established to standardise the names of the different CAIRT products. This names could have character length strings composed of fixed length sub-strings joined together by underscore character (_).

The name should contain information on the type of file (L1b, L2a, L2b), start and stop time.

4.3 Structure of the files

The files will first contain a list of dimensions and variables.

Both the observations and the retrieved products are defined on 3D grids, which may not coincide. A record variable is time and it defines the position of the observation/retrieved product in the along track direction. An altitude and across-track grid corresponds at each time (along-track position).

Where possible, dimensions should be fixed in all the data set. This allows to easily merge subsets of standard files of the same species with standard netCDF tools. On the other hand, the possibility of using non fixed dimensions allows to limit the size of the file.

Global attributes

To convey some general properties of a file, netCDF format makes available the global attributes feature. Most of the defined global attributes are self explaining and their contents deal with information about the creation of the file, references, instruments and platform identifiers and some others are needed to comply with the standard conventions. Some attributes provide information about the retrieval process (for L2 files) and the structure of the file, processor version of the used processor; auxiliary data version of the auxiliary data.

5. L1b

L1b products are the geolocated and spectrally and radiometrically calibrated spectral radiance obtained by the L1 processor starting from the CAIRT interferograms. Level-1b products are expected to be directly used for operational applications through data assimilation (e.g., into NWP and atmospheric composition models). They will hence be generated in Near Real Time (NRT). They are also the main input into the L2a processing framework, containing individual but similar processors for each trace gas product, and temperature.

Level 1b files have to contain all information needed by the L2 processor. This is:

- Information on time of measurements,
- satellite position and velocity,
- elevation and azimuth angle of each spectrum,
- information on geolocation of the tangent points: geometric and (optional) with refraction (assuming standard atmosphere),
- spectral grid information,
- **calibrated spectra**,
- NESR (on a coarser grid)
- data quality indicator,
- information on the name of used auxiliary data.

The content of this file is illustrated in Table 1. A cross-check verification with information provided in [4] has been performed.

Table 1 L1b file content

Dimensions

Name	Description
Ntime	No. of time steps. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between acquisitions (sampling measurements in the along-track direction) and time step.
N_orb_data	Number of elements to define an orbital position or velocity in ECEF. N_orb-data value=3
N_att_data	Number of elements to define an attitude quaternion in ECEF. N_att_data value=4
nband	No. of bands
Wavenumber	No. of spectral points

Wavenumber_nesr	No. of spectral points of the NESR
N_pix_act	Number of pixels in the array detector over ACT
N_pix_z	Number of pixels in the array detector over z
N_aux_files	Number of aux data files

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
Time_ret	Seconds starting from the first of January of a tbd year relative to each acquisition.	float64	ntime	sec
Satellite position	Satellite position vector (X, Y, Z) in ECEF	Float64	Ntime, n_orb_data	km
Satellite position error	Error of satellite position vector (X, Y, Z) in ECEF	Float64	Ntime, n_orb_data	km
Satellite velocity	Satellite velocity vector (X, Y, Z) in earth-fixed reference	Float64	Ntime, n_orb_data	km/s
Satellite velocity error	Error of the satellite velocity vector (X, Y, Z) in earth-fixed reference	Float64	Ntime, n_orb_data	km/s
Satellite attitude	Attitude quaternions from S/C reference frame to orbital frame	Float64	Ntime, n_att_data	degrees
Satellite attitude error	Error of attitude quaternions from S/C reference frame to orbital frame	Float64	Ntime, n_att_data	degrees
Sub satellite lat	Latitude of the Sub satellite point in geodetic coordinate (WGS84)	Float64	Ntime	degrees
Sub satellite lon	Longitude of the Sub satellite point in geodetic	Float64	Ntime	degrees

	coordinate (WGS84)			
(Sub satellite altitude)	Altitude of the Sub satellite point in geodetic coordinate (WGS84)	Float64	Ntime	km
Yaw_ppix	Azimuth of the detector pixel viewing direction with respect the satellite reference frame	Floa64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Yaw_ppix error	Error of azimuth of the detector pixel viewing direction with respect the satellite reference frame	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Pitch_ppix	elevation of the detector pixel with respect the satellite reference frame	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Pitch_ppix error	Error of the elevation of the detector pixel with respect the satellite reference frame	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Tg_lat_noref	Latitude of the pixel tangent point (no refraction)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Tg_lon_noref	Longitude of the pixel tangent point (no refraction)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
Tg_alt_noref	Altitude of the pixel tangent point (no refraction)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	km
(Tg_lat_ref) Optional	Latitude of the pixel tangent point (with refraction, standard atmosphere)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees
(Tg_lon_ref) Optional	Longitude of the pixel tangent point (with refraction, standard atmosphere)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	degrees

(Tg_alt_ref) Optional	Altitude of the pixel tangent point (with refraction, standard atmosphere)	Float64	Ntime, N_pix_act, N_pix_z, nband	km
Mopd	Maximum path difference	Float64	1	cm
earth_radius	Radius of earth surface curvature in looking direction at nadir of LOS tangent point	Float64	Ntime	km
Solar zenith angle	Solar zenith angle	Float64	Ntime,num_row,num_col?	degrees
band_validity_flag	Flag indicating if a particular band has problems	Int32	ntime, nbands	
Wavenumber	Frequency	Float64	Wavenumber	
Radiance	Radiance on the full spectral range	float32	Ntime, num_row, num_col,wavenumber	nW/cm ² sr cm ⁻¹
NESR	NESR on the full spectral range	Float64	Ntime, num_row, num_col,wavenumber_nesr	nW/cm ² sr cm ⁻¹
Measured_quality_flag	Quality flag of the measurements	Int32	Ntime, num_row, num_col	
Aux_data_name	Name of the files of the auxiliary data	string	N_aux_files	

5.1 L1b auxiliary data

L1b auxiliary data contain information needed to perform the spectral calibration, radiometric calibration, (LOS calibration) of the spectra by the L1 processor.

6. L2a

L2a products are generated by the L2a processor (see [2]), which starts from geolocated and calibrated spectra at various tangent altitudes from multiple consecutive acquisitions. The processor then performs an inversion to derive temperature and the Volume Mixing Ratio (VMR) of trace species and aerosols, corresponding to a defined 3D grid.

The 3D measurement grid is defined based on the sampling determined by the position of the tangent point of a selected spectrum (e.g., the lowest one) in each vertical sequence across all across-track positions. The retrieval grid may or may not coincide with the measurement grid. Typically, it features regular sampling and is target-dependent—often significantly coarser than the measurement grid for certain targets. L2a products will be provided in the retrieval grid.

The state vector includes both the target parameters (e.g., the 2D temperature profile) and other quantities that may interfere with the target parameters. However, only the target parameter is retained and incorporated into a 3D representation of the atmospheric state. In subsequent steps, additional trace gases and target parameters are derived using also information on the previously obtained quantities.

L2a fields will be supplied with error profiles and the diagonal elements of the Averaging Kernel (AK). The complete covariance and AK matrices, which can be very large depending on the retrieval settings, will be made available for dedicated calibration/validation (cal/val) campaigns and/or upon request (see discussion in Sect.0).

A daily file is expected for each of the geophysical quantities targeted by the mission, including temperature, the VMR of each of the 17 trace species (e.g., H₂O, O₃, CH₄), and H₂SO₄ (liquid) aerosol. The file structure for both temperature and a trace gas is outlined below. This structure is consistent for all other trace species.

Structure of the files

The record variable is time and it is the only coordinate variable. Even if retrieval in a given area is performed considering several consecutive acquisitions assumed to be measured at the same time, the time associated to each profile of the 2D grid is the time of the acquisition having the middle tangent altitude closer to the latitude of the grid profile.

Assuming that there is a file per product, Table 2 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** describes the list of variables contained in Temperature L2a file, while Table 3 describes the list of variables contained in target trace species L2a files.

Table 2 Temperature file content

Dimensions:

Name	Description
Ntime_ret	No. of time steps. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between time steps and along-track sampling in the retrieval grid.
n_z_ret	No. of altitude points of the retrieval grid
n_act_ret	No. of across-track points of the retrieval grid
n_retr	No. of different 2D retrievals performed along the orbit

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
Time_ret	Seconds starting from the first of January of a tbd year corresponding to each point of the retrieval grid.	float64	ntime	sec

	Obtained by assigning the time of the nearest acquisition. Time_ret can be a subsample of Time.			
z_ret	Altitude of the levels of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret	km
lat_ret	Latitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
lon_ret	Longitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
Pressure	3D pressure on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	Pa
Temperature**	3D temperature on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	K
Temp_uncert	Square root of the diagonal elements of the Covariance Matrix CM (CM is also provided as optional)	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	K
CM	CM (optional)	float32	(n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime) x (n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime)*	KxK
AK	Averaging Kernel (optional)	float32	(n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime)	
T_vert_res	Vertical resolution of temperature	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	km
T_hor_res	Horizontal (along track) resolution of temperature	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	km
SZA	Solar zenith angle in each point of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
QF	Quality flag	integer	n_z_ret(tbc), n_act_ret, ntime	-
Chi2	Chi-square	float32	n_act_ret, n_retr	-
IG	Initial guess	Float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	K
CI	Cloud Index	Float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	-

* Since the CM is symmetrical, only the diagonal and one half of the matrix can be stored

** Two types of products are foreseen for temperature, the one on a very fine grid to be used for the computation of the gravity waves, and the one for the retrieval of all the trace species and aerosols

Table 3 Trace species VMR file content

Dimensions:

Name	Description
Ntime_ret	No. of time steps. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between time steps and along-track sampling of the retrieval grid.
n_z_ret*	No. of altitude points of the retrieval grid
n_act_ret*	No. of across-track points of the retrieval grid
n_retr*	No. of different 2D retrievals performed along the orbit

*Dedicated values for each trace species may be needed

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
Time_ret	Seconds starting from the first of January of a tbd year corresponding to each point of the retrieval grid. Obtained by assigning the time of the nearest acquisition. Time_ret can be a subsample of time.	float64	ntime	sec
z_ret	Altitude of the levels of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret	km
lat_ret	Latitude of the retrieval grid	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
lon_ret	Longitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees

Pressure	3D pressure on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	Pa
Temperature	3D temperature on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	K
VMR	VMR profile	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	ppmv
VMR uncertainties	Square root of the diagonal elements of the Covariance Matrix (which is also provided as optional)	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	ppmv
VMR_vert_res	Vertical resolution of temperature	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	km
VMR_hor_res	Horizontal (along track) resolution of temperature	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	km
(CM) (optional)	CM	float32	See Sect.0	ppmv*ppmv
(AK) (optional)	Averaging Kernel	float32	See Sect.0	-
SZA	Solar zenith angle in each point of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
QF	Quality flag indicating the quality of the retrieval: 0 = good >0 =bad	integer	n_z_ret(tbc),n_act_ret, ntime	-
Chi2	Chi-square	float32	n_act_ret, n_retr	-
IG	Initial guess	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	ppmv

6.1 L2a Auxiliary data

The auxiliary data required for L2 analysis are:

- Spectroscopic database and/or tabulated cross-sections

The forward model is based on laboratory spectroscopic data allowing to calculate the atmospheric emission and absorption for a given atmospheric state. Provided are either parameters for individual lines, where these can be resolved, or emissivity cross section tables for trace species and/or spectral regions where this is not the case. In order to allow an uncertainty estimate for the retrieval result, these data need to be provided with uncertainties for the individual parameters. The retrieval uses spectral windows which may contain a multitude of lines. It is therefore also essential to provide guidance how the uncertainties of the individual lines have to be combined in order to estimate the uncertainty of the integrated radiance of a spectral window.

- Selected spectral intervals at the different altitudes

The availability of broadband spectra enables the selection of spectral intervals that exhibit minimal systematic errors while containing the most information relevant to the target quantities. Using carefully selected spectral intervals tailored to each retrieval target helps reduce both the computational time required for simulating observations and the associated systematic errors.

- NWP p/T (and CAMS) data and Climatological data (like ERS)
The retrieval needs a climatology of all L2a target species for a first guess of the actual atmospheric state in order to launch the iterative process. This needs to be present in the targeted altitude range of the considered species. A representative first guess per atmospheric region and season leads to fewer iterations and hence reduces computational effort. Natural variability of the L2a target species provided together with the mean state is used for regularization.
The retrieval of temperature and altitude is based on a first guess of temperature and geopotential height provided by numerical weather prediction (NWP). It is sufficient if these data are provided for a limited altitude range, i.e. they do not need to cover the entire height range of temperature data up to 110km altitude.
- ISRF, SEDF
Accurate information on the Instrument Spectral Response Function (ISRF) and the System Energy Distribution Function (SEDF) is essential for reliably simulating the spectra measured by the instrument. The quality of this information, as well as its variability over time, will need to be assessed through dedicated tests during the Commissioning Phase and beyond.

7. L2b

L2b products are products derived from L2a data, directly linked to mission objectives.

They are:

- gravity waves (GW) parameters at a subsampling of the retrieval grid
- age of air AoA at the same grid of L2a products
- Total NOy at the same grid of L2a products

7.1 Gravity waves

GW parameters are derived by the S3D wave analysis (see [3]) starting from 3D temperature profiles at the highest resolution (50 km along-track, 25 km across-track, 1 km vertical).

The outputs are gravity waves parameters at a subsampling of the retrieval grid. They are provided for each center of a cuboid, defined as (along-track * across-track * vertical).

For each cuboid center point, S3D provides individual 3D gravity waves: GW amplitude, i.e., the maximum temperature perturbation; the wave direction, which is the (horizontal) propagation direction of the GW (and perpendicular to the phase fronts); GW wavelength (both horizontal and vertical), giving the (horizontal/vertical distance between wave crests and troughs); GW Momentum Flux in the propagation direction, i.e., the wave direction from above, which can then be separated into zonal and meridional components. And finally the intrinsic phase speed, giving the speed at which the phase of the wave propagates in the wave direction for an observer moving with the background winds, and, if information on atmospheric winds is available (e.g., from reanalysis data), the ground-based phase speed, which is the speed at which the phases move relative to the ground (also in the above mentioned wave direction). Lastly, a quality flag is provided, which is necessary as the analysis always tries to describe the observations with wave perturbations, even if there are none in the first place. This quality flag, therefore, gives information of whether the determined wave parameters at a given location are valid. Only valid values should be used for further analysis.

At each analysis location, multiple waves can be detected in case they are in a superposition. To describe multiple wave modes at a single location, the additional wave component dimension `n_wc_GW` is used.

Table 4 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** describes the content of L2b GW file.

Table 4 Content of L2b GW file

Dimensions:

Name	Description
ntime_GW	No. of time steps in correspondence of sampled QW quantities. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between time steps and along-track sampling of the retrieval grid of GW.
n_z_GW	No. of altitude points of the retrieval grid for GW
n_act_GW	No. of across-track points of the retrieval grid for GW
n_wc_GW	No. of wave components used in the analysis

Content:

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
Time_GW	Average time of the acquisitions included in the cuboid	float64	ntime_GW	sec
z_GW	Altitude grid for GW retrieval	float32	n_z_GW	km
Lat_GW	Latitude on the GW retrieval grid	float32	n_act_GW, ntime_GW	degrees
Lon_GW	Longitude on the GW retrieval grid	float32	n_act_GW, ntime_GW	degrees
Pressure	Pressure on the retrieval grid for GW	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW	Pa
GW_amplitude	Amplitude of GW	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	K
GW_horizontal wave length	GW horizontal wave length	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	km
GW_vertical wave length	GW vertical wave length	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	km

GW_direction	Horizontal GW phase propagation direction	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	degree
GWMF	Absolute GW Momentum Flux in the direction of wave propagation	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	Pa
phase_speed	Intrinsic phase speed	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	[m/s]
ground-based_phase_speed	ground-based phase speed (needs ancillary winds)	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	[m/s]
Quality_flag	Quality flag describing validity of the values	int	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	-
GW_amplitude_unc.	Uncertainty on Amplitude of GW	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	K
GW_horizontal_wave_length_unc.	Uncertainty on GW horizontal wave length	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	km
GW_vertical_wave_length_unc	Uncertainty on GW vertical wave length	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	km
GW_direction_unc.	Uncertainty on Horizontal GW phase propagation direction	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	degree
GWMF_unc.	Uncertainty on Absolute GW Momentum Flux in the direction of wave propagation	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	Pa
phase_speed_unc.	Uncertainty on Intrinsic phase speed	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	[m/s]
ground-based_phase_speed_unc.	Uncertainty on ground-based phase speed	float32	n_z_GW, n_act_GW, ntime_GW, n_wc_GW	[m/s]

7.2 AoA

Age of air is determined using 3D profiles of SF6, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CH4, N2O on the 3D grid.

The outputs are 3D Age of air profiles.

3D AoA error is a combination of the contribution coming from the individual errors of the 6 used profiles plus error of the correlation method [3]. The content of L2b AoA file is listed in Table 5

Table 5 Content of L2b AoA file

Dimensions:

Name	Description
Ntime_ret	No. of time steps. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between time steps and along-track sampling of the retrieval grid.
n_z_ret	No. of altitude points of the retrieval grid
n_act_ret	No. of across-track points of the retrieval grid

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
Time	Seconds starting from the first of January of a tbd year corresponding to each point of the retrieval grid. Obtained by assigning the time of the nearest acquisition. Time_ret can be a subsample of time.	Float64	ntime_ret	sec
z_ret	Altitude of the levels of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret	km
lat_ret	Latitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
lon_ret	Longitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
Pressure	3D pressure on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	Pa
AoA	AoA on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	year
AoA_uncert	Combined contribution	float32	n_z_ret, n_act_ret, ntime	year

	coming from the individual retrieval uncertainties of the 6 used profiles + uncertainties coming from the correlation method			
Quality_flag	Quality flag	integer	n_act_ret, ntime	-

7.3 NO_y

The budget of reactive nitrogen compounds (NO_y) in the middle atmosphere enables to derive the important coupling of space weather effects in the thermosphere down into the stratosphere, useful to attribute changes in the stratospheric ozone layer from chemistry and transport.

It is computed from L2a input data of NO, NO₂, HNO₃, N₂O₅ and ClONO₂ (+HNO₄) performing the sum of NO+NO₂+HNO₃+ClONO₂+2*N₂O₅ (+HNO₄, although this is not a primary data product and provides only a marginal contribution). (Funke et al., 2016):

The outputs are:

- Total NO_y on a 3D grid

- NO_y measurement noise errors calculated as root mean square of (absolute) individual errors.

- Spatial resolution computed from the AKM given by the vmr-weighted sum of AKMs of the individual trace species.

In case the AKM of the single products are not provided as output, the spatial resolution of NO_y can be computed from the spatial resolution of the single components. Indeed, assuming that NO_y partitioning of the retrieved products is similar to the “true” partitioning, the retrieved NO_y could indeed be approximated by

$$NOy_{ret} = \frac{\sum_i AKM_i \cdot VMR_i}{\sum_i VMR_i} NOy_{true}$$

Then, since the spatial resolution is proportional to 1/AKM_{ii}, the NO_y resolution can be computed as:

$$\frac{1}{res_{NOy}} = \frac{\sum_i \frac{VMR_i}{res_i}}{\sum_i VMR_i}$$

The content of L2b NO_y file is reported in Table 6.

Table 6 Content of L2b NO_y file

Dimensions:

Name	Description
ntime	No. of time steps. There is a 1 to 1 correspondence between time steps and along-

	track sampling of the retrieval grid..
n_z_ret	No. of altitude points of the retrieval grid
n_act_ret	No. of across-track points of the retrieval grid

Name	Description	Type	Dimension	Units
L1b_file	L1b file used for the retrieval	char	ntime,len_L1b_id	
Time_ret	Seconds starting from the first of January of a tbd year corresponding to each point of the retrieval grid. Obtained by assigning the time of the nearest acquisition. Time_ret can be a subsample of time.	float64	ntime	sec
z_ret	Altitude of the levels of the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret	km
lat_ret	Latitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
lon_ret	Longitude of the grid of retrieved profiles	float32	n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
Pressure	3D pressure on the retrieval grid	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	Pa
NOy	sum of NO+NO2+HNO3+ClONO2+2*N2O5 (+HNO4, although this is not a primary data product and provides only a marginal contribution)	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	ppmv
3D NOy VMR error	NOy VMR error calculated as rms of (absolute) individual errors.	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	ppmv
NOy VMR Vertical resolution	Computed from AKM obtained by the vmr-weighted sum of individual climatological (tbc) AKMs	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	km
NOy VMR Horizontal resolution (alt)	Computed from AKM obtained by the vmr-weighted sum of individual climatological (tbc) AKMs	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	km
SZA	Solar zenith angle of the single spectrum	float32	n_z_ret,n_act_ret, ntime	degrees
QF	Quality flag	integer	n_z_ret(tbc),n_act_ret, ntime	-

7.4 L2b Auxiliary data

- NWP surface wind for GW

For the L2b processing of gravity waves horizontal wind velocities are required for the calculation of ground-based phase speed from the primary inferred wave parameters. Horizontal wind

velocities are available from NWP throughout the stratosphere in good quality. Assimilation of higher altitude data e.g. based on CAIRT temperatures or the calculation of geostrophic winds would provide horizontal wind velocities throughout the entire targeted altitudes of 20-80km.

- For AoA: Tropical SF6 time-series and ERA based ratio of AoA moments+ global model data of AoA (see Voet et al., 2024)

The inference of age of air as an L2b product relies on a mesospheric loss correction of SF6 to infer a zonal-mean based age of air via a standard method. The mesospheric loss parametrization needs to be provided with an uncertainty.

8. Appendix 1- Example of L1b and L2a data from previous limb missions

As terms of reference for CAIRT mission product specifications we provide examples of the L1b products from MIPAS on ENVISAT mission, that can be considered the heritage mission of CAIRT, and from GLORIA, which can be considered the CAIRT prototype. For the L2a products we provides examples from two previous limb missions that provided a global coverage, again MIPAS on ENVISAT and MLS on AURA, which performs a kind of tomographic retrieval.

8.1 MIPAS L1b product data

The file header of one L1b MIPAS on ENVISAT file is reported below.

```
netcdf MIPAS___1P_TABB20090605_085008_000060272079_00351_37980_0000 {
dimensions:
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (2212 currently)
    nscans = 77 ;
    nigms = 6 ;
    nbands = 5 ;
variables:
    byte product_error_flag ;
        product_error_flag:long_name = "Product confidence data information" ;
        product_error_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
        product_error_flag:flag_meanings = "no_error_in_product one_or_more_error_in_product" ;
    byte calibration_warning_flag ;
        calibration_warning_flag:long_name = "Measurement calibration quality information" ;
        calibration_warning_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b ;
        calibration_warning_flag:flag_meanings = "no_issue offset_issue gain_issue both_issues" ;

// global attributes:
    :title = "MIPAS atmospheric limb radiance spectra calibrated" ;
    :Conventions = "CF1.6" ;
    :naming_authority = "ESA" ;
    :institution = "European Space Agency (ESA)" ;
    :identifier_product_doi_authority = "https://doi.org" ;
    :identifier_product_doi = "10.57780/en1-a8b46da" ;
    :date_created = "20250830T011905Z" ;
    :level1_product_file = "MIPAS___1P_TABB20090605_085008_000060272079_00351_37980_0000.nc" ;
    :platform = "ENVISAT" ;
    :sat_id = "EN" ;
    :sensor = "MIPAS" ;
    :source = "MIPAS satellite observations" ;
    :level = "L1" ;
    :temporal = "orbital" ;
    :orbit = "37980" ;
    :time_coverage_start = "20090605T095008Z" ;
    :time_coverage_end = "20090605T113035Z" ;

group: science_measurement {
dimensions:
```

```

wavenumber_a = 4721 ;
wavenumber_ab = 2721 ;
wavenumber_b = 4881 ;
wavenumber_c = 3201 ;
wavenumber_d = 9601 ;
wavenumber_nesr = 69 ;
variables:
byte meas_quality_flag(time) ;
    meas_quality_flag:long_name = "Measurement quality indicator summary" ;
    meas_quality_flag:flag_values = "0b, 1b" ;
    meas_quality_flag:flag_meanings = "reliable_data contain_unreliable_data" ;
double time(time) ;
    time:long_name = "Measurement time at interferometer zero path difference" ;
    time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
    time:standard_name = "time" ;
ushort id_counter(time) ;
    id_counter:long_name = "Sequential id counter" ;
ushort relative_position(time) ;
    relative_position:long_name = "Relative position of current sweep in scan" ;
ushort sweeps_in_scan(time) ;
    sweeps_in_scan:long_name = "Last commanded number of sweeps in scan" ;
float height(time) ;
    height:long_name = "Height of LOS tangent point above WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    height:units = "km" ;
    height:standard_name = "Height" ;
float height_error(time) ;
    height_error:long_name = "Height error of LOS tangent point above WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    height_error:units = "km" ;
    height_error:standard_name = "Height error" ;
double earth_radius(time) ;
    earth_radius:long_name = "Radius of earth surface curvature in looking direction at nadir of LOS tangent point" ;
    earth_radius:units = "km" ;
double range_rate(time) ;
    range_rate:long_name = "Target to satellite range rate" ;
    range_rate:units = "km second-1" ;
double altitude_rate(time) ;
    altitude_rate:long_name = "Target geodetic altitude rate" ;
    altitude_rate:units = "km second-1" ;
double azimuth_angle(time) ;
    azimuth_angle:long_name = "LOS azimuth angle in topocentric coordinates" ;
    azimuth_angle:units = "degrees" ;
    azimuth_angle:valid_range = 0., 360. ;
double elevation_angle(time) ;
    elevation_angle:long_name = "LOS elevation angle in topocentric coordinates" ;
    elevation_angle:units = "degrees" ;
    elevation_angle:valid_range = -90., 90. ;
float longitude(time) ;
    longitude:long_name = "Longitude of LOS tangent point on WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
    longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
    longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
float longitude_error(time) ;
    longitude_error:long_name = "Longitude error of LOS tangent point on WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    longitude_error:units = "degrees" ;
    longitude_error:standard_name = "longitude error" ;
float latitude(time) ;
    latitude:long_name = "Latitude of LOS tangent point on WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
    latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
    latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
float latitude_error(time) ;
    latitude_error:long_name = "Latitude error of LOS tangent point on WGS84 reference ellipsoid" ;
    latitude_error:units = "degrees" ;
    latitude_error:standard_name = "latitude error" ;
byte day_night_flag(time) ;
    day_night_flag:long_name = "Daytime/nighttime at tangent point flag" ;
    day_night_flag:flag_values = "-1b, 1b" ;
    day_night_flag:flag_meanings = "nighttime_measurement daytime_measurement" ;
byte band_validity_flag(time, nbands) ;
    band_validity_flag:long_name = "Band validity flag A, AB, B, C, D" ;

```

```

        band_validity_flag:flag_values = "0b, 2b, 4b, 8b" ;
        band_validity_flag:flag_meanings = "non_corrupted corrupted_transmission_errors corrupted_observational_validation
corrupted_ADC_saturation" ;
        double wavenumber_a(wavenumber_a) ;
            wavenumber_a:long_name = "Band A wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_a:units = "cm-1" ;
        double wavenumber_ab(wavenumber_ab) ;
            wavenumber_ab:long_name = "Band AB wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_ab:units = "cm-1" ;
        double wavenumber_b(wavenumber_b) ;
            wavenumber_b:long_name = "Band B wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_b:units = "cm-1" ;
        double wavenumber_c(wavenumber_c) ;
            wavenumber_c:long_name = "Band C wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_c:units = "cm-1" ;
        double wavenumber_d(wavenumber_d) ;
            wavenumber_d:long_name = "Band D wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_d:units = "cm-1" ;
        float limb_spectral_radiance_a(time, wavenumber_a) ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_a:long_name = "Atmospheric limb spectral radiance band A" ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_a:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
        float limb_spectral_radiance_ab(time, wavenumber_ab) ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_ab:long_name = "Atmospheric limb spectral radiance band AB" ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_ab:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
        float limb_spectral_radiance_b(time, wavenumber_b) ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_b:long_name = "Atmospheric limb spectral radiance band B" ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_b:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
        float limb_spectral_radiance_c(time, wavenumber_c) ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_c:long_name = "Atmospheric limb spectral radiance band C" ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_c:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
        float limb_spectral_radiance_d(time, wavenumber_d) ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_d:long_name = "Atmospheric limb spectral radiance band D" ;
            limb_spectral_radiance_d:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
        double wavenumber_nesr(wavenumber_nesr) ;
            wavenumber_nesr:long_name = "NESR wavenumber" ;
            wavenumber_nesr:units = "cm-1" ;
        float nesr(time, wavenumber_nesr) ;
            nesr:long_name = "NESR of measurement" ;
            nesr:units = "W cm-2 sr-1 (cm-1)-1" ;
    } // group science_measurement

group: processor {
    dimensions:
        ndet_nonlin = 4 ;
        noffsets = UNLIMITED ; // (16 currently)
        nspikes = 10 ;
        ndir = 2 ;
        npts_off_a = 1177 ;
        npts_off_ab = 687 ;
        npts_off_b = 1123 ;
        npts_off_c = 824 ;
        npts_off_d = 355 ;
    variables:
        double doppler_factor(time) ;
            doppler_factor:long_name = "Doppler correction factor applied on spectral axis" ;
        ushort detected_spikes(time, nigms) ;
            detected_spikes:long_name = "Number of spikes detected and corrected in interferogram A1, A2, AB, B, C, D" ;
        uint spike_positions(time, nigms, nspikes) ;
            spike_positions:long_name = "Spike positions in the interferogram of highest first 10" ;
        double spike_amplitudes_real(time, nigms, nspikes) ;
            spike_amplitudes_real:long_name = "Spike amplitudes real part value of highest first 10" ;
        double spike_amplitudes_imag(time, nigms, nspikes) ;
            spike_amplitudes_imag:long_name = "Spike amplitudes imaginary part value of highest first 10" ;
        ushort remaining_spikes(time, nigms) ;
            remaining_spikes:long_name = "Number of remaining detected and corrected spikes" ;
        double average_spike_amplitudes_real(time, nigms) ;
            average_spike_amplitudes_real:long_name = "Average amplitudes real part of remaining spikes" ;
        double average_spike_amplitudes_imag(time, nigms) ;
            average_spike_amplitudes_imag:long_name = "Average amplitudes imaginary part of remaining spikes" ;
        short fce(time) ;

```

```

        fce:long_name = "Fringe count error value calculated and corrected" ;
byte detector_flux_flag(time, ndet_nonlin) ;
    detector_flux_flag:long_name = "Detector non-linearity flux validity A1, A2, B1, B2" ;
    detector_flux_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
    detector_flux_flag:flag_meanings = "valid outside_valid_range" ;
int acc_gain_fce(nscans) ;
    acc_gain_fce:long_name = "Accumulated FCE corrected in gain calibration data, at end of current scan" ;
byte offset_band_validity_flag(noffsets, nbands) ;
    offset_band_validity_flag:long_name = "Band validity flag A, AB, B, C, D" ;
    offset_band_validity_flag:flag_values = 0b, 2b, 4b ;
    offset_band_validity_flag:flag_meanings = "non_corrupted corrupted_transmission_errors
corrupted_observational_validation" ;
short acc_offset_fce(noffsets) ;
    acc_offset_fce:long_name = "Accumulated FCE correction in gain calibration data, at end of offset measurement sequence" ;
byte offset_direction_flag(noffsets) ;
    offset_direction_flag:long_name = "Offset sweep direction" ;
    offset_direction_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
    offset_direction_flag:flag_meanings = "forward reverse" ;
byte offset_flux_flag(noffsets, ndet_nonlin) ;
    offset_flux_flag:long_name = "Offset detector non-linearity flux validity A1, A2, B1, B2" ;
    offset_flux_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
    offset_flux_flag:flag_meanings = "valid outside_valid_range" ;
double offset_time_a(noffsets) ;
    offset_time_a:long_name = "ZPD crossing time of first sweep in currently valid offset sequence for this band a" ;
    offset_time_a:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
double offset_time_ab(noffsets) ;
    offset_time_ab:long_name = "ZPD crossing time of first sweep in currently valid offset sequence for this band ab" ;
    offset_time_ab:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
double offset_time_b(noffsets) ;
    offset_time_b:long_name = "ZPD crossing time of first sweep in currently valid offset sequence for this band b" ;
    offset_time_b:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
double offset_time_c(noffsets) ;
    offset_time_c:long_name = "ZPD crossing time of first sweep in currently valid offset sequence for this band c" ;
    offset_time_c:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
double offset_time_d(noffsets) ;
    offset_time_d:long_name = "ZPD crossing time of first sweep in currently valid offset sequence for this band d" ;
    offset_time_d:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
ubyte offset_dec_factor_a(noffsets) ;
    offset_dec_factor_a:long_name = "Offset decimation factor a" ;
ubyte offset_dec_factor_ab(noffsets) ;
    offset_dec_factor_ab:long_name = "Offset decimation factor ab" ;
ubyte offset_dec_factor_b(noffsets) ;
    offset_dec_factor_b:long_name = "Offset decimation factor b" ;
ubyte offset_dec_factor_c(noffsets) ;
    offset_dec_factor_c:long_name = "Offset decimation factor c" ;
ubyte offset_dec_factor_d(noffsets) ;
    offset_dec_factor_d:long_name = "Offset decimation factor d" ;
float offset_a_real(noffsets, npts_off_a) ;
    offset_a_real:long_name = "Offset a real part" ;
float offset_a_imag(noffsets, npts_off_a) ;
    offset_a_imag:long_name = "Offset a imaginary part" ;
float offset_ab_real(noffsets, npts_off_ab) ;
    offset_ab_real:long_name = "Offset ab real part" ;
float offset_ab_imag(noffsets, npts_off_ab) ;
    offset_ab_imag:long_name = "Offset ab imaginary part" ;
float offset_b_real(noffsets, npts_off_b) ;
    offset_b_real:long_name = "Offset b real part" ;
float offset_b_imag(noffsets, npts_off_b) ;
    offset_b_imag:long_name = "Offset b imaginary part" ;
float offset_c_real(noffsets, npts_off_c) ;
    offset_c_real:long_name = "Offset c real part" ;
float offset_c_imag(noffsets, npts_off_c) ;
    offset_c_imag:long_name = "Offset c imaginary part" ;
float offset_d_real(noffsets, npts_off_d) ;
    offset_d_real:long_name = "Offset d real part" ;
float offset_d_imag(noffsets, npts_off_d) ;
    offset_d_imag:long_name = "Offset d imaginary part" ;
ushort number_of_sweeps_phase_B(nscans, ndir) ;
    number_of_sweeps_phase_B:long_name = "Number of sweeps for which the phase parameter exceeds threshold, forward B,
reverse B" ;

```

```

        ushort number_of_sweeps_phase_C(nscans, ndir) ;
        number_of_sweeps_phase_C:long_name = "Number of sweeps for which the phase parameter exceeds threshold, forward C,
reverse C" ;
        ushort number_of_sweeps_opd(nscans, ndir) ;
        number_of_sweeps_opd:long_name = "Number of sweeps for which the OPD shift in band C differ from band B, forward,
reverse" ;

// group attributes:
:level1_product_file = "MIP_NL__1PYABB20090605_085008_000060272079_00351_37980_0000.N1" ;
:processing_stage = "Y" ;
:reference_document = "PO-TN-BOM-GS-0010_7" ;
:acquisition_station = "PDHS-K" ;
:processing_center = "ABB" ;
:processing_time = "20250202T104737Z" ;
:processor_version = "MICAL/08.04" ;
:level0_product_file = "MIP_NL__OPPLRA20090605_085007_000060302079_00351_37980_9541.N1" ;
:ils_spectral_cal_file = "MIP_CS1_AXVABB20170304_130315_20090605_000000_20090705_000000" ;
:gain_cal_file = "MIP_CG1_AXVABB20170304_130735_20090605_000000_20090705_000000" ;
:los_cal_file = "MIP_CL1_AXT__20160331_082029_20020401_000000_20161214_000000" ;
:instrument_char_file = "MIP_CA1_AXVABB20170301_163826_20090605_000000_20090705_000000" ;
:offset_val_file = "MIP_CO1_AXVABB20170304_130813_20090605_000000_20090705_000000" ;
:microwindows_file = "MIP_MW1_AXT__20120105_091859_20020401_000000_20161214_000000" ;
:processing_parameters_file = "MIP_PS1_AXT__20160531_153245_20040809_000000_20161214_000000" ;
:dor_vor_file = "DOR_VOR_AXVF-P20160701_142900_20090604_215526_20090606_002326" ;
:aux_fra_file = "AUX_FRA_AXVFOS20090609_180501_20090605_000000_20090607_000000" ;
:mipnas_netcdf_translator_version = "MINET/0.1" ;

} // group processor

group: scan {
variables:
    int first_meas_id_scan(nscans) ;
        first_meas_id_scan:long_name = "id_counter of the first measurement in the scan" ;
    double first_time(nscans) ;
        first_time:long_name = "Measurement time at the beginning of scan" ;
        first_time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
    double mid_time(nscans) ;
        mid_time:long_name = "Measurement time in the middle of scan" ;
        mid_time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
    double last_time(nscans) ;
        last_time:long_name = "Measurement time at the end of scan" ;
        last_time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
    float first_longitude(nscans) ;
        first_longitude:long_name = "WGS84 longitude of first measurement in the scan" ;
        first_longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        first_longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
        first_longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
    float first_latitude(nscans) ;
        first_latitude:long_name = "WGS84 latitude of first measurement in the scan" ;
        first_latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        first_latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
        first_latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
    float mid_longitude(nscans) ;
        mid_longitude:long_name = "WGS84 longitude of middle measurement in the scan" ;
        mid_longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        mid_longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
        mid_longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
    float mid_latitude(nscans) ;
        mid_latitude:long_name = "WGS84 latitude of middle measurement in the scan" ;
        mid_latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        mid_latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
        mid_latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
    float last_longitude(nscans) ;
        last_longitude:long_name = "WGS84 longitude of last measurement in the scan" ;
        last_longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        last_longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
        last_longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
    float last_latitude(nscans) ;
        last_latitude:long_name = "WGS84 latitude of last measurement in the scan" ;
        last_latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        last_latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;

```

```

        last_latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
    ushort nb_sweeps_scan(nscans) ;
        nb_sweeps_scan:long_name = "Number of sweeps in current scan" ;
    ushort number_of_corrupted_sweeps(nscans) ;
        number_of_corrupted_sweeps:long_name = "Number of corrupted sweeps in scan" ;
    ushort number_of_corrupted_sweeps_inst(nscans) ;
        number_of_corrupted_sweeps_inst:long_name = "Number of corrupted sweeps in scan with instrument errors" ;
    ushort number_of_corrupted_sweeps_obs(nscans) ;
        number_of_corrupted_sweeps_obs:long_name = "Number of corrupted sweeps in scan with observational errors" ;
    ushort number_of_sweeps_flux(nscans) ;
        number_of_sweeps_flux:long_name = "Number of sweeps for which the detector flux is out of range" ;
    double true_local_solar_time(nscans) ;
        true_local_solar_time:long_name = "True local solar time at target" ;
        true_local_solar_time:units = "hours" ;
        true_local_solar_time:valid_range = 0., 24. ;
    double sat_target_azimuth_angle(nscans) ;
        sat_target_azimuth_angle:long_name = "Satellite to target azimuth" ;
        sat_target_azimuth_angle:units = "degrees" ;
        sat_target_azimuth_angle:valid_range = 0., 360. ;
    double target_sun_azimuth_angle(nscans) ;
        target_sun_azimuth_angle:long_name = "Target to sun azimuth" ;
        target_sun_azimuth_angle:units = "degrees" ;
        target_sun_azimuth_angle:valid_range = 0., 360. ;
    double target_sun_elevation_angle(nscans) ;
        target_sun_elevation_angle:long_name = "Target to sun elevation" ;
        target_sun_elevation_angle:units = "degrees" ;
        target_sun_elevation_angle:valid_range = -90., 90. ;
    byte scan_day_night_flag(nscans) ;
        scan_day_night_flag:long_name = "Scan daytime/nighttime" ;
        scan_day_night_flag:flag_values = -1b, 0b, 1b ;
        scan_day_night_flag:flag_meanings = "nighttime_scan solar_terminator_scan daytime_scan" ;

// group attributes:
        :number_of_nominal_scans = "00077" ;
        :number_of_special_event_scans = "00000" ;
        :sweeps_per_nominal_scan = "00029" ;
        :scans_per_offset_calibration = "00012" ;
} // group scan

group: instrument {
    dimensions:
        ndetectors = 8 ;
        nangles = 2 ;
        npos = 2 ;
        auxlen = 1400 ;
    variables:
        double instrument_azimuth_angle(time) ;
            instrument_azimuth_angle:long_name = "Instrument azimuth pointing angle" ;
            instrument_azimuth_angle:units = "degrees" ;
            instrument_azimuth_angle:valid_range = 0., 360. ;
        double instrument_elevation_angle(time) ;
            instrument_elevation_angle:long_name = "Instrument elevation pointing angle" ;
            instrument_elevation_angle:units = "degrees" ;
            instrument_elevation_angle:valid_range = -90., 90. ;
        ushort sweep_id_counter(time) ;
            sweep_id_counter:long_name = "Sequential id counter in source packet" ;
        ushort mode_activity(time) ;
            mode_activity:long_name = "Instrument mode/activity" ;
        uint cmd_fringe_count(time, npos) ;
            cmd_fringe_count:long_name = "Commanded left & right fringe count" ;
        uint gate_position(time, npos) ;
            gate_position:long_name = "APS position at last scan gate start & stop" ;
        ushort aux_warning_flag(time) ;
            aux_warning_flag:long_name = "Warning flag in the ISP auxiliary data" ;
        ushort aux_error_flag(time) ;
            aux_error_flag:long_name = "Error flag in the ISP auxiliary data" ;
        byte sweep_direction_flag(time) ;
            sweep_direction_flag:long_name = "Sweep direction" ;
            sweep_direction_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
            sweep_direction_flag:flag_meanings = "forward reverse" ;

```

```

ubyte aux_data(time, auxlen) ;
    aux_data:long_name = "Auxiliary data from source packet" ;
short min_adc(time, ndetectors) ;
    min_adc:long_name = "Interferogram minimum ADC value detector A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2, D1, D2" ;
short max_adc(time, ndetectors) ;
    max_adc:long_name = "Interferogram maximum ADC value detector A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2, D1, D2" ;
short app_proc_id(nscans) ;
    app_proc_id:long_name = "Application process ID" ;
short filter_set_id(nscans) ;
    filter_set_id:long_name = "Filter set ID" ;
ubyte dec_factor(nscans, ndetectors) ;
    dec_factor:long_name = "Decimation factor detector A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2, D1, D2" ;
ubyte band_mapping(nscans, nignms) ;
    band_mapping:long_name = "Band mapping configuration" ;
ubyte sait_id(nscans, nangles) ;
    sait_id:long_name = "Commanded elevation and azimuth SAIT ID of current scan" ;
uint cmd_start_angle(nscans, nangles) ;
    cmd_start_angle:long_name = "Commanded start elevation and azimuth angles of current scan" ;
uint scan_counter(nscans) ;
    scan_counter:long_name = "Elevation scan counter" ;
float paw_gain(nscans, ndetectors) ;
    paw_gain:long_name = "PAW gain scaling constant detector A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2, D1, D2" ;

// group attributes:
    :number_of_fringes_per_scene_sweep = "0000124800" ;
    :mpd = "8" ;
    :mpd_units = "cm" ;
} // group instrument

group: satellite {
dimensions:
    xyz = 3 ;
variables:
    double satellite_position(time, xyz) ;
        satellite_position:long_name = "Satellite position vector (X, Y, Z) in earth-fixed reference" ;
        satellite_position:units = "km" ;

// group attributes:
    :orbit_phase = "2" ;
    :orbit_cycle = "079" ;
    :relative_orbit = "00351" ;
    :state_vector_time = "20090605T095026Z" ;
    :delta_ut1 = "0.247203" ;
    :delta_ut1_units = "second" ;
    :state_vector_x_pos = "-6839.219460" ;
    :state_vector_y_pos = "-2049.752908" ;
    :state_vector_z_pos = "593.295005" ;
    :state_vector_pos_units = "km" ;
    :state_vector_x_vel = "0.125207" ;
    :state_vector_y_vel = "1.742153" ;
    :state_vector_z_vel = "7.351602" ;
    :state_vector_vel_units = "km second-1" ;
    :state_vector_source = "FR" ;
    :utc_sbt_time = "20090605T083304Z" ;
    :sbt_time = "2856990464" ;
    :sbt_clock_step = "3906250475" ;
    :sbt_clock_step_units = "psecond" ;
    :leap_time = "20090101T000000Z" ;
    :leap_sign = "001" ;
    :leap_error = "0" ;
} // group satellite

```

8.2 GLORIA L1b product data

The file header of one L1b GLORIA file is reported below as an example of a L1b product of a limb instruments using array detectors.

```

netcdf \20250319_114315_bincal {
dimensions:

```

```

len_cubname = 20 ;
num_img = 1 ;
num_supi = 127 ;
num_row = 128 ;
num_col = 48 ;
num_isw = 11201 ;
variables:
float abscissa(num_isw) ;
    abscissa:long_name = "spectral abscissa values." ;
    abscissa:units = "cm-1" ;
char cubname(num_img, len_cubname) ;
    cubname:long_name = "cuboid file name" ;
double meastime(num_img) ;
    meastime:standard_name = "time" ;
    meastime:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00" ;
short ifg_direction(num_img) ;
    ifg_direction:long_name = "interferogram direction. 0:forward, 1:backward" ;
short meastype(num_img) ;
    meastype:long_name = "measurement type. 0:chemistry, 1:dynamics, 2:bb1, 3:bb2, 4:deepspace" ;
float yaw(num_img) ;
    yaw:long_name = "instrument azimuth angle (ecef)." ;
    yaw:units = "degree" ;
float yaw_rms(num_img) ;
    yaw_rms:long_name = "instrument azimuth angle residual mean square (ecef)." ;
    yaw_rms:units = "degree" ;
float pitch(num_img) ;
    pitch:long_name = "instrument elevation angle (ecef)" ;
    pitch:units = "degree" ;
float pitch_rms(num_img) ;
    pitch_rms:long_name = "instrument elevation angle residual mean square (ecef)" ;
    pitch_rms:units = "degree" ;
float roll(num_img) ;
    roll:long_name = "instrument roll angle (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    roll:units = "degree" ;
float roll_rms(num_img) ;
    roll_rms:long_name = "instrument roll angle residual mean square (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    roll_rms:units = "degree" ;
float g_a(num_img) ;
    g_a:long_name = "instrument azimuth angle (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_a:units = "degree" ;
float g_a_rms(num_img) ;
    g_a_rms:long_name = "instrument azimuth angle residual mean square (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_a_rms:units = "degree" ;
float g_e(num_img) ;
    g_e:long_name = "instrument elevation angle (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_e:units = "degree" ;
float g_e_rms(num_img) ;
    g_e_rms:long_name = "instrument elevation angle residual mean square (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_e_rms:units = "degree" ;
float g_b(num_img) ;
    g_b:long_name = "instrument rotation angle (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_b:units = "degree" ;
float g_b_rms(num_img) ;
    g_b_rms:long_name = "instrument rotation angle residual mean square (carrier fixed coordinate system)." ;
    g_b_rms:units = "degree" ;
float latitude(num_img) ;
    latitude:long_name = "instrument position (latitude)." ;
    latitude:units = "degree" ;
float longitude(num_img) ;
    longitude:long_name = "instrument position (longitude)." ;
    longitude:units = "degree" ;
float altitude(num_img) ;
    altitude:long_name = "instrument position (altitude)." ;
    altitude:units = "km" ;
float itc(num_img) ;
float tint(num_img) ;
float yaw_ppix(num_img, num_row, num_col) ;
    yaw_ppix:long_name = "detectorpixel azimuth (ecef)." ;
    yaw_ppix:units = "degree" ;
float pitch_ppix(num_img, num_row, num_col) ;

```

```

        pitch_ppix:long_name = "detectorpixel elevation (ecef).";
        pitch_ppix:units = "degree";
float laser_wavelength(num_img);
float velocity(num_img);
float fce_shift(num_img);
        fce_shift:units = "cm";
float mopd(num_img);
        mopd:units = "cm";
float zopd(num_img);
        zopd:units = "cm";
float radiance(num_img, num_row, num_col, num_isw);
        radiance:long_name = "calibrated radiance values.";
        radiance:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0788.2000_0796.2000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0788.2000_0796.2000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0788.2000_0796.2000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0791.0000_0793.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0791.0000_0793.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0791.0000_0793.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0819.0000_0821.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0819.0000_0821.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0819.0000_0821.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0820.0000_0821.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0820.0000_0821.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0820.0000_0821.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0830.6000_0831.2000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0830.6000_0831.2000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0830.6000_0831.2000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0831.0000_0832.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0831.0000_0832.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0831.0000_0832.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0832.0000_0834.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0832.0000_0834.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0832.0000_0834.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0832.4000_0834.4000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0832.4000_0834.4000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0832.4000_0834.4000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0947.6000_0950.4000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0947.6000_0950.4000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0947.6000_0950.4000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_0960.0000_0961.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_0960.0000_0961.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_0960.0000_0961.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_1224.0000_1224.6000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_1224.0000_1224.6000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_1224.0000_1224.6000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_1225.0000_1226.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_1225.0000_1226.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_1225.0000_1226.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";
float radiance_mw_1406.0000_1407.0000(num_img, num_row, num_col);
        radiance_mw_1406.0000_1407.0000:least_significant_digit = 1;
        radiance_mw_1406.0000_1407.0000:units = "nW / (cm^2 sr cm^-1)";

// global attributes:
:file_type = "GLORIA_PREINPUT";
:file_version = "0.4";
:gloripy_version = "2631";
:gloripy_revision = "87f2da3a53cd3cde8fa3a4a83511d33b46725d0e";
:controlfile =
:date_created = "2025-05-22T15:22:15.621120";
:date_modified = "2025-05-22T15:22:15.621120";
:history = "2025-05-22T15:22:15.621120: /home/labor/share/GEXE/latest/bin_spectra.py --single binned --nadir2 ctl.py .";
:instrument = "GLORIA";
:supi_offset_absolute = 65;
:supi_offset_relative = 1;

```

8.3 L2a of MIPAS

MIPAS ESA processor provides two files, the standard file provides the information generally needed by data users (mainly geolocation information, altitude, pressure, temperature, retrieved profile and related

Covariance Matrices (CMs) and Averaging Kernels (AKs), quality flags, . . .). It covers a single orbit and a single species. When the species are obtained by a Multi Target Retrieval, a number of standard files equal to the number of retrieved species (including temperature, if retrieved) are generated.

This is an example of the file header of the standard file for temperature:

```
netcdf MIPAS_2PS_TEMP____20111111T231120_20111112T005203_50734_00 {
dimensions:
    len_L1b_id = 62 ;
    extended_level = 121 ;
    cmdim = 378 ;
    level = 27 ;
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (96 currently)
variables:
    double time(time) ;
        time:long_name = "Scan time (ZPD time of sweep closest to scans mean time)" ;
        time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
        time:standard_name = "time" ;
    char L1b_id(time, len_L1b_id) ;
        L1b_id:long_name = "L1b file used for the retrieval" ;
    int processor_patchlevel(time) ;
        processor_patchlevel:long_name = "Patch level of the processor" ;
    byte auxdata_subversion(time) ;
        auxdata_subversion:long_name = "Subversion of auxiliary files" ;
    int orbit_id(time) ;
        orbit_id:long_name = "Orbit sequential number" ;
    int scan_id(time) ;
        scan_id:long_name = "Scan counter in the L1b file" ;
    byte obs_mode_flag(time) ;
        obs_mode_flag:long_name = "Observation mode flag" ;
        obs_mode_flag:flag_values = -1b, 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b ;
        obs_mode_flag:flag_meanings = "fr_nominal rr17 or_nominal or_utls1 or_middle_atm or_upper_atm or_nlc or_ae
or_utls1_old or_utls2" ;
        obs_mode_flag:chi2_Threshold = "3.6 4.0 3.5 3.2 3.9 3.4 3.6 6.9 20.0 20.0" ;
        obs_mode_flag:lambda_Threshold = "10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0 10.0" ;
        obs_mode_flag:max_err_Threshold = "1.3E+00 2.7E+00 8.6E+00 2.2E+00 1.2E+01 1.1E+01 1.2E+01 3.0E+00 1.0E+03 1.0E+03"
;
    float chi2(time) ;
        chi2:long_name = "Final normalized chi square" ;
        chi2:valid_min = 0.f ;
        chi2:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    float lambda_marq(time) ;
        lambda_marq:long_name = "Final Marquardt dumping parameter" ;
        lambda_marq:valid_min = 0.f ;
        lambda_marq:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    byte day_night(time) ;
        day_night:long_name = "Three level Day/Night flag" ;
        day_night:flag_values = -1b, 0b, 1b ;
        day_night:flag_meanings = "nighttime_scan undef daytime_scan" ;
    float longitude(time) ;
        longitude:long_name = "Longitude of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
        longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
        longitude:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    float latitude(time) ;
        latitude:long_name = "Latitude of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
        latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
        latitude:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    float solar_zenith_angle(time) ;
        solar_zenith_angle:long_name = "Solar zenith angle of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
        solar_zenith_angle:units = "degrees" ;
        solar_zenith_angle:valid_range = 0.f, 180.f ;
        solar_zenith_angle:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    float orbital_coordinate(time) ;
        orbital_coordinate:long_name = "Orbital coordinate of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
        orbital_coordinate:units = "degree from equator (ascending)" ;
        orbital_coordinate:valid_range = 0.f, 365.f ;
        orbital_coordinate:reference = "TN_UNIBO-IAC_MR-LS_2016_ORMHG_v1.0 - Tech note: implementation of the horizontal
gradients in ORM V8" ;
```

```

        orbital_coordinate: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float ECMWF_altitude_shift(time) ;
    ECMWF_altitude_shift:long_name = "ECMWF altitude shift wrt retrieved altitude" ;
    ECMWF_altitude_shift:units = "m" ;
    ECMWF_altitude_shift: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    ECMWF_altitude_shift:comment = "Z_ecmwfcorrected - Z_retrieved, (a)if this variable is set to a valid value, the ECMWF
pressure profile was used to place the lowermost altitude used in pT retrieval, (b)if this variable is set to _FillValue, the lowermost altitude used in
pT retrieval was set to its engineering estimate" ;
byte quality_flag(time) ;
    quality_flag:long_name = "Quality flag for the retrieval" ;
    quality_flag:standard_name = "air_temperature_status_flag" ;
    quality_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
    quality_flag:flag_meanings = "reliable_data unreliable_data" ;
byte conv_id(time) ;
    conv_id:long_name = "Convergency flag" ;
    conv_id:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 5b, 6b, 7b ;
    conv_id:flag_meanings = "convergence_reached max_macro_exceed max_micro_exceed convergence_reached_sing_mat
max_macro_exceed_sing_mat max_micro_exceed_sing_mat" ;
byte post_quality_flag(time) ;
    post_quality_flag:long_name = "A posteriori quality flag" ;
    post_quality_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b ;
    post_quality_flag:flag_meanings = "reliable_data unreliable_data" ;
float pressure(time, level) ;
    pressure:long_name = "Pressure" ;
    pressure:units = "hPa" ;
    pressure:standard_name = "air_pressure" ;
    pressure:valid_range = 0.f, 10000.f ;
    pressure:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    pressure: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float pressure_error(time, level) ;
    pressure_error:long_name = "Pressure error" ;
    pressure_error:units = "hPa" ;
    pressure_error:standard_name = "air_pressure_standard_error" ;
    pressure_error:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    pressure_error: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float height(time, level) ;
    height:long_name = "Height" ;
    height:units = "km" ;
    height:standard_name = "height_above_reference_ellipsoid" ;
    height:valid_range = 0.f, 200.f ;
    height:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    height: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    height:comment = "(a)If the variable ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to a valid value this variable reports the tangent heights of
the scan, anchored to the lowermost altitude used in pT retrieval as obtained from ECMWF pressure profile; (b)if the variable
ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to the _FillValue it reports the tangent heights of the scan anchored to the engineering estimate the lowermost
altitude used in pT retrieval" ;
    height:reference = "IFAC_GA_2007_12_SC issue:7 Rev:0 - High level algorithm definition and physical and mathematical
optimisations (MIPAS Level 2 Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document)" ;
float height_error(time, level) ;
    height_error:long_name = "Height error" ;
    height_error:units = "km" ;
    height_error:standard_name = "height_above_reference_ellipsoid_standard_error" ;
    height_error:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    height_error: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    height_error:comment = "It is the error of the retrieved tangent heights, assuming the lowest tangent altitude as known and
hence with 0 error. To get the total error of heights one should add to this error component the error of the lowermost height: (a)If the variable
ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to a valid value, the error obtained from the ECMWF ERA Interim pressure profile; (b)if the variable
ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to the _FillValue, the engineering pointing error. According to Multi-TASTE validation, this uncertainty generally
consists of: (a)150m; (b)600m. Reference: https://earth.esa.int/documents/700255/2621625/TN-BIRA-IASB-MultiTASTE-Phase-F-MIPAS-ML2PP7-Iss1-RevB/34f7f395-75ef-46c4-855e-a0f9d225e7c2 ;
float cloud_index(time, level) ;
    cloud_index:long_name = "Cloud detection index" ;
    cloud_index:units = "1" ;
    cloud_index:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    cloud_index: FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    cloud_index:references = "IFAC_GA_2007_12_SC issue:7 Rev:0 - High level algorithm definition and physical and
mathematical optimisations (MIPAS Level 2 Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document)" ;
float profile(time, level) ;
    profile:long_name = "Vertical profile of temperature" ;
    profile:units = "K" ;

```

```

        profile:standard_name = "air_temperature" ;
        profile:valid_range = 0.f, 400.f ;
        profile:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
        profile:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float profile_error(time, level) ;
    profile_error:long_name = "Standard error of Vertical profile of temperature" ;
    profile_error:units = "K" ;
    profile_error:standard_name = "air_temperature_standard_error" ;
    profile_error:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    profile_error:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float covariance_matrix(time, cmdim) ;
    covariance_matrix:long_name = "Covariance matrix of Vertical profile of temperature" ;
    covariance_matrix:units = "K**2" ;
    covariance_matrix:comment = "First i elements of row #i" ;
    covariance_matrix:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float averaging_kernel(time, level, level) ;
    averaging_kernel:long_name = "Averaging kernel of Vertical profile of temperature" ;
    averaging_kernel:units = "1" ;
    averaging_kernel:comment = "the rows of the matrix are the averaging kernels" ;
    averaging_kernel:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_height(time, extended_level) ;
    extended_height:long_name = "Extended height" ;
    extended_height:units = "km" ;
    extended_height:valid_range = 0.f, 200.f ;
    extended_height:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    extended_height:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_pressure(time, extended_level) ;
    extended_pressure:long_name = "Extended pressure" ;
    extended_pressure:units = "hPa" ;
    extended_pressure:valid_range = 0.f, 10000.f ;
    extended_pressure:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    extended_pressure:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_profile(time, extended_level) ;
    extended_profile:long_name = "Extended Vertical profile of temperature" ;
    extended_profile:units = "K" ;
    extended_profile:valid_range = 0.f, 400.f ;
    extended_profile:missing_value = -88888.8f ;
    extended_profile:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;

// global attributes:
:title = "Level 2 MIPAS products - simplified file" ;
:Conventions = "CF1.6 ACDD-1.3" ;
:species = "Temperature" ;
:retrieval_type = "Levenberg-Marquardt" ;
:platform = "ENVISAT" ;
:sat_id = "EN" ;
:sensor = "MIPAS" ;
:source = "MIPAS satellite observations" ;
:level = "L2" ;
:temporal = "orbital" ;
:product_type = "MIPAS_2PS_" ;
:orbit = "50734" ;
:comment = "MIPAS reprocessing 2018" ;
:id = "MIPAS_2PS_TEMP___20111111T231120_20111112T005203_50734_00.nc" ;
:naming_authority = "ESA" ;
:institution = "European Space Agency (ESA)" ;
:date_created = "2019-04-06T10:49:17Z" ;
:creator_name = "MIPAS Quality Working Group (QWG)" ;
:creator_url = "https://earth.esa.int/web/guest/missions/esa-operational-eo-missions/envisat/instruments/mipas" ;
:creator_email = "eohelp@esa.int" ;
:processor_version = "ORM_V8.xx" ;
:auxdata_version = "9.xx" ;
:references = "https://earth.esa.int/web/sppa/mission-performance/esa-missions/envisat/mipas/products-and-
algorithms/products-information" ;
:reference_document = "IFAC_GA_2018_1_FB issue:2.0 -- MIPAS L2 V8 output data definition" ;
:time_coverage_start = "2011-11-11T23:11:20Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "2011-11-12T00:52:03Z" ;
:geospatial_lat_min = -87.13848f ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 88.23206f ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -178.1288f ;

```

```

        :geospatial_lon_max = 164.7936f ;
    }

```

The extended file is thought for expert users and for diagnostics. It completes the information obtained from the retrieval including the full state vector (retrieved profiles, atmospheric continuum and instrumental offset) with related CM and AK, and also with additional information about the retrieval process. This information is useful when making data fusion [8, 9, 10]. Due to the composition of the state vector, variables in the file are heterogeneous, i.e. their elements do not have the same units. The file covers a single orbit and a single retrieval. If the file is the result of a MTR, it includes information about several species.

We have to note that the number of provided output files is different in the case of pressure and temperature (pT), single target or multi-target retrieval (see table 7.5). In particular, for pT and single target VMR retrieval one standard and one extended file is provided. In case of multi-target retrieval, one extended file is provided, while the number of standard files is equal to the number of retrieved species of multi-target retrieval, or a sub-sample of it if some of those are considered to be not reliable.

This is an example of the file header of the extended file:

```

netcdf MIPAS_2PE_PT_____20111111T231120_20111112T005203_50734_00 {
dimensions:
    len_L1b_id = 62 ;
    extended_level = 121 ;
    n_gradients = 2 ;
    cmdim = 5886 ;
    parameters = 108 ;
    mwindows = 6 ;
    targets = 4 ;
    species = 1 ;
    level = 27 ;
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (96 currently)
variables:
    double time(time) ;
        time:long_name = "Scan time (ZPD time of sweep closest to scans mean time)" ;
        time:units = "seconds since 2000-01-01 00:00:00 UTC" ;
        time:standard_name = "time" ;
    char L1b_id(time, len_L1b_id) ;
        L1b_id:long_name = "L1b file used for the retrieval" ;
    int processor_patchlevel(time) ;
        processor_patchlevel:long_name = "Patch level of the processor" ;
    byte auxdata_subversion(time) ;
        auxdata_subversion:long_name = "Subversion of auxiliary files" ;
    int orbit_id(time) ;
        orbit_id:long_name = "Orbit sequential number" ;
    int scan_id(time) ;
        scan_id:long_name = "Scan counter in the L1b file" ;
    byte obs_mode_flag(time) ;
        obs_mode_flag:long_name = "Observation mode flag" ;
        obs_mode_flag:flag_values = -1b, 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b ;
        obs_mode_flag:flag_meanings = "fr_nominal rr17 or_nominal or_utls1 or_middle_atm or_upper_atm or_nlc or_ae
or_utls1_old or_utls2" ;
    float chi2(time) ;
        chi2:long_name = "Final normalized chi square" ;
        chi2:valid_min = 0.f ;
        chi2:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    int gauss_iterations(time) ;
        gauss_iterations:long_name = "Number of Gauss iterations performed" ;
    int marquardt_iterations(time) ;
        marquardt_iterations:long_name = "Number of Marquardt iterations performed" ;
    float lambda_marq(time, targets) ;
        lambda_marq:long_name = "Final Marquardt dumping parameters" ;
        lambda_marq:valid_min = 0.f ;
        lambda_marq:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
    byte day_night(time) ;
        day_night:long_name = "Three level Day/Night flag" ;
        day_night:flag_values = -1b, 0b, 1b ;
        day_night:flag_meanings = "nighttime_scan undef daytime_scan" ;
    float longitude(time) ;

```

```

longitude:long_name = "Longitude of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
longitude:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float latitude(time) ;
latitude:long_name = "Latitude of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
latitude:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float solar_zenith_angle(time) ;
solar_zenith_angle:long_name = "Solar zenith angle of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
solar_zenith_angle:units = "degrees" ;
solar_zenith_angle:valid_range = 0.f, 180.f ;
solar_zenith_angle:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float orbital_coordinate(time) ;
orbital_coordinate:long_name = "Orbital coordinate of LOS tangent point closest to scans mean time" ;
orbital_coordinate:units = "degree from equator (ascending)" ;
orbital_coordinate:valid_range = 0.f, 365.f ;
orbital_coordinate:reference = "TN_UNIBO-IAC_MR-LS_2016_ORMHG_v1.0 - Tech note: implementation of the horizontal
gradients in ORM V8" ;
orbital_coordinate:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float ECMWF_altitude_shift(time) ;
ECMWF_altitude_shift:long_name = "ECMWF altitude shift wrt retrieved altitude" ;
ECMWF_altitude_shift:units = "m" ;
ECMWF_altitude_shift:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
ECMWF_altitude_shift:comment = "Z_ecmwfcorrected - Z_retrieved, (a)if this variable is set to a valid value, the ECMWF
pressure profile was used to place the lowermost altitude used in pT retrieval, (b)if this variable is set to _FillValue, the lowermost altitude used in
pT retrieval was set to its engineering estimate" ;
byte conv_id(time) ;
conv_id:long_name = "Convergency flag" ;
conv_id:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 5b, 6b, 7b ;
conv_id:flag_meanings = "convergence_reached max_macro_exceed max_micro_exceed convergence_reached_sing_mat
max_macro_exceed_sing_mat max_micro_exceed_sing_mat" ;
float longitude_profile(time, level) ;
longitude_profile:long_name = "Longitude of LOS tangent points" ;
longitude_profile:units = "degree_east" ;
longitude_profile:standard_name = "longitude" ;
longitude_profile:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float latitude_profile(time, level) ;
latitude_profile:long_name = "Latitude of LOS tangent points" ;
latitude_profile:units = "degree_north" ;
latitude_profile:standard_name = "latitude" ;
latitude_profile:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float orbital_coordinate_profile(time, level) ;
orbital_coordinate_profile:long_name = "Orbital coordinate of LOS tangent points" ;
orbital_coordinate_profile:units = "degree from equator (ascending)" ;
orbital_coordinate_profile:valid_range = 0.f, 365.f ;
orbital_coordinate_profile:reference = "TN_UNIBO-IAC_MR-LS_2016_ORMHG_v1.0 - Tech note: implementation of the
horizontal gradients in ORM V8" ;
orbital_coordinate_profile:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float height(time, level) ;
height:long_name = "Height" ;
height:units = "km" ;
height:standard_name = "height_above_reference_ellipsoid" ;
height:valid_range = 0.f, 200.f ;
height:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
height:comment = "(a)If the variable ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to a valid value this variable reports the tangent heights of
the scan, anchored to the lowermost altitude used in pT retrieval as obtained from ECMWF pressure profile; (b)if the variable
ECMWF_altitude_shift is set to the _FillValue it reports the tangent heights of the scan anchored to the engineering estimate the lowermost
altitude used in pT retrieval" ;
height:reference = "IFAC_GA_2007_12_SC issue:7 Rev:0 - High level algorithm definition and physical and mathematical
optimisations (MIPAS Level 2 Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document)" ;
int nparam_per_target(time, targets) ;
nparam_per_target:long_name = "Number of parameter for each target" ;
nparam_per_target:only_one_continuum_profile = "F" ;
nparam_per_target:_FillValue = -99999 ;
byte param_units_flag(time, targets) ;
param_units_flag:long_name = "Flag indicating the measurement units of each target" ;
param_units_flag:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b ;
param_units_flag:flag_meanings = "hPa K 1E-6 1 nW/(cm^2 sr cm^{-1})" ;

```

```

        param_units_flag:_FillValue = -99b ;
int selected_occupation_matrix_flag(time) ;
        selected_occupation_matrix_flag:occupation_matrix_label_prefix = "OM_PT__" ;
        selected_occupation_matrix_flag:flag_meanings = "1:nominal 501:utls1 701:ma 801:ua 601:ae 901:nlc 401:utls1_old
301:utls2" ;
        selected_occupation_matrix_flag:comment = "The name of the selected occupation matrix can be obtained concatenating
the occupation_matrix_label_prefix with the selected_occupation_matrix_flag, as a 3 digit zero padded integer" ;
        selected_occupation_matrix_flag:_FillValue = -99999 ;
byte effective_occupation_matrix(time, mwindows, level) ;
        effective_occupation_matrix:_FillValue = -99b ;
byte retrieval_vectors(time, species, level) ;
        retrieval_vectors:_FillValue = -99b ;
float state_vector(time, parameters) ;
        state_vector:long_name = "Array of all the retrieved parameters" ;
        state_vector:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float full_covariance_matrix(time, cmdim) ;
        full_covariance_matrix:long_name = "Covariance matrix of all retrieved parameters" ;
        full_covariance_matrix:comment = "First i elements of row #i" ;
        full_covariance_matrix:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float full_averaging_kernel(time, parameters, parameters) ;
        full_averaging_kernel:long_name = "Averaging kernel of all retrieved parameters" ;
        full_averaging_kernel:comment = "the rows of the matrix are the averaging kernels" ;
        full_averaging_kernel:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_height(time, extended_level) ;
        extended_height:long_name = "Extended height" ;
        extended_height:units = "km" ;
        extended_height:valid_range = 0.f, 200.f ;
        extended_height:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_left_gradient(time, n_gradients, extended_level) ;
        extended_left_gradient:long_name = "Left gradient on the extended grid" ;
        extended_left_gradient:units = "km" ;
        extended_left_gradient:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;
float extended_right_gradient(time, n_gradients, extended_level) ;
        extended_right_gradient:long_name = "Right gradient on the extended grid" ;
        extended_right_gradient:units = "km" ;
        extended_right_gradient:_FillValue = -99999.9f ;

// global attributes:
:title = "Level 2 MIPAS products - extended file" ;
:species = "Pressure,Temperature" ;
:retrieval_type = "Levenberg_Marquardt" ;
:platform = "ENVISAT" ;
:sat_id = "EN" ;
:sensor = "MIPAS" ;
:source = "MIPAS satellite observations" ;
:level = "L2" ;
:temporal = "orbital" ;
:product_type = "MIPAS_2PE_" ;
:orbit = "50734" ;
:comment = "MIPAS reprocessing 2018" ;
:id = "MIPAS_2PE_PT_____20111111T231120_20111112T005203_50734_00.nc" ;
:naming_authority = "ESA" ;
:institution = "European Space Agency (ESA)" ;
:date_created = "2019-04-06T10:49:17Z" ;
:creator_name = "MIPAS Quality Working Group (QWG)" ;
:creator_url = "https://earth.esa.int/web/guest/missions/esa-operational-eo-missions/envisat/instruments/mipas" ;
:creator_email = "eohelp@esa.int" ;
:processor_version = "ORM_V8.xx" ;
:auxdata_version = "9.xx" ;
:references = "https://earth.esa.int/web/sppa/mission-performance/esa-missions/envisat/mipas/products-and-
algorithms/products-information" ;
:reference_document = "IFAC_GA_2018_1_FB issue:2.0 -- MIPAS L2 V8 output data definition" ;
:time_coverage_start = "2011-11-11T23:11:20Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "2011-11-12T00:52:03Z" ;
}

```

8.4 MLS L2a products

MLS products resemble in same sense CAIRT data since the MLS retrieval algorithms are “tomographic”. They indeed use information from multiple consecutive limb scans to simultaneously estimate the 2-dimensional (along-track and vertical) state of the atmosphere over multiple Level 2 profiles. Information on the products can be found in [6], the format of the files is HDF5.

Each file contains data fields L2gpValue and L2gpPrecision, which describe the value and precision (reported at 1σ) of the VMR of the trace species of interest, respectively. In addition to these fields, fields such as latitude etc. describe geolocation information.

Representative vertical, horizontal and 2-D averaging kernels have been archived for each MLS standard product on the MLS website. Two sets of kernels are provided, each comprising five files corresponding to five broad latitude bands. One set contains 1-D (horizontal and vertical) kernels, the other the full 2-D kernels, making ten files in all. As the averaging kernels vary little with latitude, a file for a single latitude will generally be globally representative.

9. Appendix 2 – L1b/L2a/L2b product file size estimation

This appendix provides a preliminary estimation of the data volume for all CAIRT Level 1b, Level 2a, and Level 2b products.

The purpose of this estimation is to give an approximate understanding of the data volumes involved — to support sanity checks, align expectations between science and technical teams, and enable high-level qualitative comparisons with similar or past missions.

A summary of the estimated size ranges is presented in Table 7, while detailed calculations and assumptions are provided in the subsequent sub-sections.

Table 7 Summary of Estimated Data Volume Ranges for all CAIRT Products. Values in bold represent the most plausible estimates based on the current mission baseline. Values in parentheses correspond to the threshold values defined in the observation and measurement requirements. Optional data are indicated in [square brackets].

Product	Total size per day	
L1b	1.2-1.3 (0.6-0.65) Tbyte	
L2a	T for GW	0.4 Gbyte
	T+17 trace species +H ₂ SO ₄ liq	(0.1)- 1.3 Gbyte
	Full diagnostics (AK and CM) OPTIONAL	T for GW [555Gbyte] T+trace+aerosol [(0.1)-1.1Tbyte]
L2b	NO _y	(7)- 123 Mbyte
	AoA	(1.6)- 33 Mbyte
	GW	210 Mbyte

9.1 L1b product size estimation

The largest quantity contained in the L1b file is given by the calibrated spectra.

The file size estimation for one day of calibrated spectral data is based on parameters established by the observation and measurement requirements (threshold and goal values) detailed in the [1], along with derived quantities from orbit track data provided by the ESA Future Missions and Instrument Division, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Parameters used for L1b product size calculation

Parameter	Name	Assumed value
Frequency step	fstep*	0.1(0.2) cm ⁻¹
Measurement range	freq_range	718-2200 cm ⁻¹
No. of spectra of an acquisition in vertical direction	n_pixel_z	110
No. of spectra of an acquisition in the across-track direction (assuming a swath of 400 km)	n_pixel_act	16
No. of acquisitions per orbit 1	n_alt	821
No. of orbits per day	norbitperday	14.22
No. of bytes per number (assumed real *4)	nbytes	4

The size of the files is computed as:

$$(\text{freq_range}/\text{fstep}) * \text{n_pixel_z} * \text{n_pixel_act} * \text{n_alt} * \text{n_orbitperday} * \text{nbytes}$$

The total dimension of calibrated spectra measured in one day results 1.2 (0.6) Tbytes/day for Goal (Threshold) requirements.

9.2 L2a product size estimation

The estimated size of the retrieval products depends on several choices that have not been finalized yet. These include decisions related to:

- The retrieval grid, which will most likely also be the grid on which the products are delivered;
- Whether a 2D or 3D retrieval is performed;
- The spatial extent of the region used for each retrieval.

As these decisions are still under discussion, the current size estimates are based on a set of assumptions, described below.

Three different retrieval grid configurations have been considered:

1. Minimum Size Configuration

In this approach, the vertical and across-track sampling grids are defined by the required spatial resolution specified in [1]. For example, if the vertical resolution requirement is 1 km, the grid spacing will also be 1 km. Note that if horizontal resolution requirements vary with altitude, the value at the lowest altitudes is applied throughout. Both threshold and goal values are considered and reported.

1. Realistic Upper Bound

This configuration assumes:

- A horizontal grid corresponding to the goal resolution of 100 km for trace species, with four across-track profiles per acquisition, assuming horizontal averaging is applied to reduce noise,
 - A vertical grid with 1 km spacing across the altitude range of interest for each species. This setup represents a likely upper limit for realistic operational use.
2. Configuration for Temperature for Gravity Waves (GW)
 This assumes the retrieval grid matches the full measurement grid, with:
- 1 km vertical spacing across the full vertical range,
 - 25 km across-track spacing, without averaging.
- This configuration is applicable to temperature retrievals used for gravity wave (GW) analysis but is considered unlikely for temperature to be used in trace species retrievals, where coarser grids (as in Configurations 1 or 2) would be preferred to improve the precision of the retrieved temperature profile.

For consistency with L1b data assumptions, a swath width of 400 km is considered in all configurations.

All numerical values used in the above scenarios are provided in Table 9.

Table 9 Definition of no. of points in each vertical profile and no. of across-track profiles per acquisition for the three cases considered for L2a file size estimation

3D Product	Minimum size with grid defined by Goal(Threshold) vertical and horizontal resolution		Medium size with grid defined by relevant altitude range and Goal vertical resolution		Extreme case with grid defined by measurement grid (only for temperature used for GW)	
	#points per vertical profile <i>n_z</i>	#across-track profiles per acquisition <i>n_{act}</i>	#points per vertical profile <i>n_z</i>	#across-track profiles per acquisition <i>n_{act}</i>	#points per vertical profile <i>n_z</i>	#across-track profiles per acquisition <i>n_{act}</i>
Temperature	86(44)	8(2)	110	4	110	16
H2O	56(28)	4(2)	110	4		
O3	56(31)	4(2)	110	4		
CH4	39(19)	4(2)	110	4		
SF6	16(6)	4(1)	30	4		
HCFC-22, CFC-11, CFC-12	16(6)	4(2)	30	4		
N2O	26(13)	4(2)	30	4		

CO	60(34)	4(2)	50	4		
NO	52(24)	4(1)	75	4		
NO2, HNO3	39(19)	4(2)	75	4		
N2O5, ClONO2	26(13)	4(1)	75	4		
PAN, OCS, SO2, H2SO4liq	26(14)	4(2)	35	4		

Table 10 summarises the total size of the files containing all L2a products for one day for the 3 different cases described in Table 1, for 3 different types of output files:

1. 1 file per product per day, with no.5 3D quantities for temperature (temperature, temperature error, pressure, temperature vertical resolution, temperature horizontal resolution) and some redundancy in each VMR trace species file (pressure grid and temperature)
2. Same as 1., but with redundancy of only pressure in VMR trace species file
3. Only one file for all products and no redundancy

The size of each file including *nprof* 3D quantities is given by:

$$\text{size} = nprof * (nz) * (nact) * (nalt) * (norbitperday (=14.22)) * (nbytes (=4))$$

Table 10 Total size of the files containing all L2a products and L2b of one day for different choices of the file organization (1 file per product, with either small or large redundancy, or a unique file with no redundancy) and different vertical and horizontal grids. Also the size of the optional full diagnostics (AK and CM) for all retrievals, discussed in Sect. 0, is reported for comparison.

L2 product total size per day			
File content	Minimum size with grid defined by Goal(Threshold) vertical and horizontal resolution	Medium size with grid defined by relevant altitude range and Goal vertical resolution	Extreme case with grid defined by measurement grid (only for temperature for GW)
L2a			
ALL L2a PRODUCTS except AK and CM. One file per product: no.5 3D quantities in Temperature file and pressure grid in all VMR files (no. 5 3D quantities)	0.7(0.1)Gbyte	1.1Gbyte	0.4 Gbyte
ALL L2a PRODUCTS except AK and CM.	0.8(0.1)Gbyte	1.3Gbyte	

One file per product: pressure and temperature in each VMR file (no.5 3D for T and no.6 3D for VMR)			
ALL L2a PRODUCTS except AK and CM. A unique file and no redundancy (no.5 3D for T and no.4 3D for VMR)(and hence a common grid required for all products)	N/A since a common grid has to be used	0.9 Gbyte	
Full diagnostics (optional)			
AK and CM of all L2a products for a extension of the 2D region of 2000 km	709(135)Gbyte	1.1Tbyte	370 +185= 555Gbyte
L2b			
NOy, with pressure and temperature in VMR files (no. 6 3D) for finest grid of NOy components (NO)	58(7) Mbyte	123 Mbyte	
AoA, with pressure and temperature (no. 6 3D) for grids of SF6	18 (1.6) Mbyte	33 Mbyte	
GW	210 Mbyte		

9.3 L2b product size estimation

For the L2b products, the size estimation was performed as follows.

The file structure for NOy is assumed to be the same of other trace species, including profiles of pressure, temperature, NOy, NOy uncertainty, and vertical and horizontal resolution—resulting in a total of six three-dimensional (3D) quantities. The vertical and horizontal grids are assumed to correspond to those of the NOy component with the finest resolution, namely NO.

Similarly, the file structure for AoA is assumed to follow the same layout as that of other trace species, also containing six 3D quantities. The adopted grid corresponds to that of SF₆.

For GW, the size estimation assumes that gravity-wave analysis is performed using overlapping analysis cuboids, with values provided for every third acquisition along-track and for three parallel tracks, corresponding to a 400 km swath. Values are included for all altitude levels within the 20–80 km range.

These numbers are preliminary and subject to revision. Based on the above assumptions, the dimensions have the values reported in Table 11.

Table 11 Assumed dimensions used in the GW analysis

Dimension	Size
N_z_GW	60
N_act_GW	3
Ntime_nwc	821/3
N_wc	5

The GW size estimation reported in Table 10, and equal to about 210 Mbyte, refer to 15 quantities of dimension ($N_z_GW * N_act_GW * Ntime_nwc * N_wc$) times the number of orbits in one day time times 4 bytes.

9.4 Full diagnostics of L2a products

Up to now we have considered, in the file contents of each file, in addition to the vertical profiles of temperature or vmr, the vertical profiles of uncertainties (given by the square root of the diagonal elements of the CM) and of the vertical and horizontal resolution, computed from the AK. Full diagnostics of retrieved 2D or 3D fields include:

- Averaging Kernels (AK), which characterize the sensitivity of the retrieval to the true atmospheric state and the influence of a priori information.
- Covariance Matrices (CM), which quantify the uncertainty and correlations between retrieved parameters.

The dimension of both the AK and CM is determined by the state vector size n , with:

- AK: $n \times n$ matrix.
- CM: also $n \times n$, but as it is symmetric ($CM_{ij} = CM_{ji}$), only $n(n+1)/2$ elements need to be stored (i.e., diagonal plus either upper or lower triangle).

The value of n depends on:

- The retrieval vertical grid (which defines the vertical resolution and extent),
- The spatial domain of the analysis (i.e., the number of profiles retrieved simultaneously in the along track direction),
- Whether a 2D or 3D retrieval is performed.

Larger domains and higher-dimensional retrievals naturally result in larger state vectors, increasing the size of the diagnostic matrices.

Two retrieval strategies have been implemented in CEEPS:

1. 2D Tomographic Retrieval:

- Generally operates on large orbit segments (or “chunks”) to reduce edge effects and to minimise redundant computations at boundaries.
 - However, for large regions (e.g., half an orbit), computing full diagnostics becomes increasingly challenging since it requires matrix inversions. In such cases, full diagnostics may be limited to representative profiles or approximated.
2. 2D Sequential Retrieval:
- Proceeds stepwise along the along track (ALT) dimension, using a sliding window (“parameter cube”) centered around each ALT grid point (see Section 7.1 of [2]).
 - More memory-efficient than 2D-tomographic retrieval but computationally intensive.
 - Edge effects are inherently reduced due to continuous progression.

Assuming the same horizontal extent (i.e., equal retrieval region size), and ignoring overlapping areas (necessary in 2D retrieval to minimize border effects), the total size of diagnostic matrices should be comparable for both methods.

Key observations:

- In 2D Tomographic Retrieval:
 - AK dimension: $(nz \times nalt) \times (nz \times nalt)$
 - Diagnostics required for $\sim 821/nalt$ regions to cover a full orbit.
- In 2D Sequential Retrieval:
 - AK dimension per window: $(nz \times nalt) \times nz$
 - Diagnostics required for all 821 acquisitions in an orbit.

To provide a rough estimate of diagnostic data volume, we assume:

- A 2D tomographic retrieval,
- A region ~ 2000 km wide, covering $nalt_ret=41$ vertical profiles (sampled every 50 km),
- Coverage of the full orbit via $nalt/nalt_ret=20$ such regions, ignoring overlap requirements,
- This region size is large enough to capture sufficient LOS overlap for retrieval while remaining manageable for computing full diagnostics.

For each trace species the size of the diagnostics can be computed as follows:

$$size_AK = [(nalt_ret) \times (nz)]^2 \times (nact) \times (nalt/nalt_ret) \times (norbitperday) \times (nbyte)$$

$$size_CM = [(nalt_ret \times nz) \times (nalt_ret \times nz + 1) \times 0.5d0] \times (nact) \times (nalt/nalt_ret) \times (norbitperday) \times (nbytes4)$$

The results for all targets are reported in Table 10.

Details of the computations are reported for all retrievals and 3 cases of vertical and horizontal grids in Table 12.

Table 12 Details of AK and CM size computation for all retrievals and 3 cases: Vertical and horizontal grid driven by requirements (case 1.Goal; case 2. Threshold) and vertical grid defined by relevant altitude range and Goal horizontal and vertical resolution (case 3) (see Table 9)

nz,nact,nalt=	86.00000000000000	8.00000000000000	41.00000000000000	
temperature 1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	113.28528437755604	56.658706466199682	169.94399084375573	
nz,nact,nalt=	44.00000000000000	2.00000000000000	41.00000000000000	
temperature 2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	7.4134772361732182	3.7087933512451938	11.122270587418411	
nz,nact,nalt=	110.00000000000000	4.00000000000000	41.00000000000000	
temperature 3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	92.668465452165222	46.344506391875534	139.01297184404078	
nz,nact,nalt=	56.00000000000000	4.00000000000000	41.00000000000000	

h2o	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	24.017215508924806	12.013837984320618	36.031053493245423
nz,nact,nalt=		28.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
h2o2	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	3.0021519386156008	1.5023835267723542	4.5045354653879546
nz,nact,nalt=		110.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
h2o	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	92.668465452165222	46.344506391875534	139.01297184404078
nz,nact,nalt=		56.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
o3	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	24.017215508924806	12.013837984320618	36.031053493245423
nz,nact,nalt=		31.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
o3	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	3.6799336900632555	1.8414144979388123	5.5213481880020678
nz,nact,nalt=		110.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
o3	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	92.668465452165222	46.344506391875534	139.01297184404078
nz,nact,nalt=		60.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
co	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	27.570783109735110	13.790995372572786	41.361778482307898
nz,nact,nalt=		34.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
co	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	4.4266423992852477	2.2149089479924395	6.6415513472776873
nz,nact,nalt=		110.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
co	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	92.668465452165222	46.344506391875534	139.01297184404078
nz,nact,nalt=		52.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	20.708721535756592	10.359217409889496	31.067938945646091
nz,nact,nalt=		24.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	1.1028313243894043	0.55197604396522526	1.6548073683546296
nz,nact,nalt=		110.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	92.668465452165222	46.344506391875534	139.01297184404078
nz,nact,nalt=		16.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
sf6	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	1.9605890211367190	0.98178886195642101	2.9423778830931400
nz,nact,nalt=		6.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
sf6	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	6.8926957774337771E-002	3.4603574329799651E-002	0.10353053210413743
nz,nact,nalt=		30.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
sf66	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	6.8926957774337776	3.4491497975695040	10.341845575003282
nz,nact,nalt=		16.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
hfcf22,f11,f12	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	1.9605890211367190	0.98178886195642101	2.9423778830931400
nz,nact,nalt=		6.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
hfcf22,f11,f12	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	0.13785391554867554	6.9207148659599302E-002	0.20706106420827486
nz,nact,nalt=		30.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
hfcf22,f11,f12	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	6.8926957774337776	3.4491497975695040	10.341845575003282
nz,nact,nalt=		26.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	5.1771803839391479	2.5910185129751739	7.7681988969143223
nz,nact,nalt=		13.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	0.64714754799239349	0.32418085424759674	0.97132840223999029
nz,nact,nalt=		50.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	19.146377159538272	9.5778584278568282	28.724235587395096
nz,nact,nalt=		39.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no2,hno3	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	11.648655863863084	5.8279704134399415	17.476626277303026
nz,nact,nalt=		19.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no2,hno3	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	0.69118421545933151	0.34603574329799652	1.0372199587573281
nz,nact,nalt=		75.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
no2,hno3	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	43.079348608961105	21.546679076612094	64.626027685573206
nz,nact,nalt=		39.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
ch4	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	11.648655863863084	5.8279704134399415	17.476626277303026
nz,nact,nalt=		19.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
ch4	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	1.3823684309186630	0.69207148659599305	2.0744399175146562
nz,nact,nalt=		75.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
ch4	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	43.079348608961105	21.546679076612094	64.626027685573206

nz,nact,nalt=	26.000000000000000	4.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o5,clono2	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	5.1771803839391479	2.5910185129751739	7.7681988969143223
nz,nact,nalt=	13.000000000000000	1.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o5,clono2	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	0.32357377399619675	0.16209042712379837	0.48566420111999514
nz,nact,nalt=	75.000000000000000	4.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
n2o5,clono2	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	43.079348608961105	21.546679076612094	64.626027685573206
nz,nact,nalt=	26.000000000000000	4.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
pan,ocs,so2,H2SO4liq	1 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	5.1771803839391479	2.5910185129751739	7.7681988969143223
nz,nact,nalt=	14.000000000000000	2.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
pan,ocs,so2, H2SO4liq	2 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	0.75053798465390020	0.37592277105922700	1.1264607557131272
nz,nact,nalt=	35.000000000000000	4.000000000000000	41.000000000000000	
pan,ocs,so2, H2SO4liq	3 ak, cm, ak+cm [Gbyte]=	9.3817248081737521	4.6941312977482612	14.075856105922012
tot=	433.01259790088250	40.766606343531521	1144.5900399591667	

9.5 Possible Compression of the data

The estimated size of the full diagnostic data is necessarily approximate, as it is based on a set of assumptions. However, the order of magnitude of the estimate is considered reasonable. In particular, the diagnostics are expected to be roughly three orders of magnitude larger than the corresponding Level 2a (L2a) data volume described earlier. Without significant compression, storing full diagnostics over the entire mission duration would be prohibitive.

At present, compression techniques can offer moderate savings—typically factors rather than orders of magnitude. The following approaches can be considered:

Lossless Compression Options

- NetCDF Internal Compression
Variables such as the CM and AK can be stored using NetCDF with lossless compression (e.g. zlib). Tests indicate at least ~15% compression is achievable.
- Integer Representation
If the dynamic range of CM or AK values is not too large, storing as integers with appropriate offset and scaling (rather than 32-bit floats) can reduce size by up to a factor of 2.
- Exploiting Optimal Estimation
If the retrieval is based on Optimal Estimation, only the posterior covariance (S_{tot}) and the a priori covariance (S_a) need to be stored. The averaging kernel (A) can be reconstructed as:
 $A = I - S_{tot} S_a^{-1}$

Similarly, the noise covariance can be derived as:
 $S_{noise} = A S_{tot}$.

This approach avoids the need to store the AK explicitly, offering both size and complexity reduction.

Lossy Compression Options

- Principal Component Decomposition
As done for IASI and IASI-NG [e.g., ref. 11], CM and AK matrices can be expressed in terms of principal components, storing only the most significant eigenvalues and eigenvectors. This method can substantially reduce storage requirements while preserving most of the diagnostic information.

However, this technique may be less effective for CAIRT, as its measurements are expected to have a high number of degrees of freedom, potentially limiting the efficiency of the principal component approach.

9.6 Actual community needs of full diagnostics data

While full averaging kernels (AK) and covariance matrices (CM) are typically provided for each nadir measurements—where retrievals are more strongly influenced by a priori information—this is not always the case for limb observations. As shown in the overview of L2a products from previous limb missions (Appendix 1), the availability of these diagnostics varies.

Given the significant data volume required to store full diagnostics, a careful assessment of the trade-offs between storing complete vs. subset diagnostic data is needed, based on the actual needs of the user community.

Validated CAIRT L2a data can serve various scientific purposes, either on their own or in combination with other datasets and models, including:

- Validation of other products (after independent validation),
- Assimilation into data assimilation (DA) systems (e.g., NWP or chemistry models),
- Combination with other products through data fusion techniques.

For the validation of CAIRT products—and their use in validating other datasets—information on precision, accuracy, and spatial resolution is essential, along with the averaging kernel matrix (AKM). However, full diagnostics for every profile may not be necessary; representative AKs and CMs might be sufficient.

In DA applications, AKs are typically not used for vertical profile assimilation from limb sounders, as their vertical resolution is usually high enough that the influence of the AK (and a priori) is minimal. Additionally, CMs have not been used in chemical DA—possibly because, apart from MIPAS (ESA), no other instruments have routinely provided CM data. Evaluating the potential impact of CAIRT AK and CM on DA applications would be valuable. If a significant impact is identified, parameterizing AK and CM for practical use could be considered, as storing these matrices for every profile would be unmanageable in operational DA systems.

Conversely, rigorous data fusion methods [8, 9 and 10] require full diagnostics per profile—both AK and CM—for the entire state vector, including variables retrieved solely to support the analysis but not included in the standard output. These methods also require access to the a priori state vector. Without these quantities, rigorous data fusion becomes challenging, and synergistic retrievals of the measurements to be combined may offer a more feasible alternative.

However, if providing AKs for each profile is not possible, a user-friendly alternative would be to offer an additional dataset that is free of formal prior information, known as the *maximum-likelihood product* (ML product), as described in [7], characterised by having the AK equal to unity. This product would not replace

the standard L2a data, but could be offered alongside it, giving users the option to choose between otherwise identical datasets.

The current proposal is to store all standard L2a products along with associated uncertainties and spatial resolution, and to conduct validation campaigns—particularly during the commissioning phase—where full diagnostics (AKs and CMs) are generated to build a representative climatology. Additionally, the L2a retrieval code should support optional full diagnostic output upon request. If rigorous data fusion is pursued, we should also explore the possibility of either parameterizing the AKs and CMs or the feasibility of using the ML product as an alternative for data fusion applications. More effective compression technique should also be searched.

10. Reference documents

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